

PROSPECTS OF INCREASING AND IMPROVING PROFITABILITY OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN NAMANGAN REGION

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Abstract: In this article, information is given about measures to improve the profitability of industrial enterprises in the Namangan region.

Key words: industrial enterprises, profitability, social infrastructure, joint venture.

Increasing the profitability of industrial enterprises in the Namangan region is closely related to the profound quality changes that are taking place in today's economy and social life. Such features are, firstly, the change of the demographic situation in the area, i.e. natural reproduction and migration movements, secondly, the transport geographical location of the region, thirdly, meeting the needs of society and eliminating socio-ecological problems, fourthly, scientific the state of using technical achievements, fifthly, the indicators of participation in the domestic and foreign markets, sixthly, the steady development of the process of intensification of the entire national economic complex. These features require the implementation of regional forecasting aimed at the complex development of increasing the profitability of industrial enterprises in the region.

The above processes, in turn, determine the political, socio-economic, ideological relations of society, which strongly influence the pace of socio-economic development of the regions and lead to the further improvement of the profitability of industrial enterprises and the formation of investment space.

Projects have been developed to attract foreign investments to the region's economy and establish industrial enterprises based on them. The main goal of the development of these programs is the comprehensive use of local natural raw material resources and production reserves in order to increase the profitability of industrial enterprises in the region in the near future and to increase their sustainable growth, to increase the volume of exports, and to improve their composition. Also, as priorities of the program:

- production of consumer goods, production of import-substituting products and increasing the export potential of the region;
- expansion of enterprises processing agricultural products;
- implementation of large-scale technological re-equipment in local and light industrial enterprises;
- entering the world market with competitive products in electrical engineering and mechanical engineering complexes;
- radical renewal of the chemical industry technologies of the region can be shown.[1]

The analysis of the main directions of establishment of joint ventures involving foreign investments in the near future shows that joint ventures in the region will be established more in the field of industrial production.

The analysis of the factors determining the investment situation is of great importance in determining the prospects for the establishment of joint ventures in regional cities and

districts. These factors include raw materials, minerals, population and labor resources, market economy, transport, social infrastructure, ecology, electric energy and other factors.

The analysis shows that there are not the same favorable conditions for increasing the profitability of industrial enterprises in all regions of the region. For example, the raw material factor has high ratings in Kosonsoy, Mingbulok, Pop and Yangikurgan districts. From the point of view of the minerals factor, good indicators were recorded in Pop, Kosonsoy, Chust and Yangikurgan districts. Therefore, there are opportunities to create a favorable investment space based on raw materials and minerals in these districts. At the moment, the ecological factor is rated very low in the city of Namangan, Mingbulok, Namangan, and Turaqorgan districts. Social infrastructure networks have a high score in the city of Namangan in the region, while they have average indicators in all other regions of the region.[3]

Other conditions were also considered in the same way. In particular, the factor of labor resources received a high rating in the city of Namangan, Chust, Kosonsoy, Pop and Torakorgan districts, and electric energy received an average rating. Of course, such an assessment does not have absolute accuracy, and it only represents a general situation to a certain extent. However, despite this, its results are more objective and can be widely used to increase the profitability and development of industrial enterprises in the region.

Based on the above analysis, it is necessary to pay great attention to the development of the city of Chust, which ranks next to Namangan, the capital of the region.

Thus, the conducted research shows that in order to increase the profitability of industrial enterprises in the region and ensure their future development, it is necessary to pay more attention to the system of the following activities:

- ☐ Operative decision to issue foreign and domestic loans to facilitate the investment space in regional districts and implement investment projects;
 - ☐ improving attraction of foreign investments through the securities market, ensuring their active participation in privatization processes in the regional industrial complex;
 - ☐ to develop targeted regional programs to encourage foreign investors and ensure regional organization of joint ventures in machine-building, light and food, and chemical industries;
 - ☐ creation of structures that accelerate the use of leasing and franchise relations in order to introduce modern technologies and encourage them;
 - ☐ expanding cooperation of the regional industrial complex with commercial banks and foreign financial institutions;
 - ☐ establish active cooperation with international engineering companies;
 - ☐ development of modern market infrastructure systems in the region and its districts, etc.
- [2]

The implementation of these measures will have a positive effect on attracting foreign investments to the industrial complex of Namangan region and accelerating their activities.

Conclusion:

Factors affecting profitability change are given special importance in the analysis. Factors affecting the change in profitability can be determined in relation to the units involved in them. For example, if the change in profitability in relation to the sale of products is affected by the change in the amount of gross profit from sales and the change in the amount of revenue received from sales, the profitability of fixed assets is affected by the change in the net profit of the enterprise and the change in the average annual value of fixed assets, the total

profitability is the amount of net profit corresponding to one amount of revenue changes, changes in the turnover of fixed assets and changes in the turnover of tangible assets are affected, etc.

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